

**Preventing, Avoiding
and Mitigating
environmental
impacts of fishing
gears and associated
marine litter**

Every year, tons of fishing gear are **discarded** to the ocean globally, inflicting **severe threats** to marine habitats and wildlife while causing **economic damage** to the **fishing sector**. The timely **tracking** and **recovery** of lost fishing gear can **minimize** this **risk**, help preserve our oceans and boost the fishing sector.

Through collaboration between the fisheries industry, scientists and NGOs, the NETTAG+ project aims to:

PREVENT

**FISHERS AS GUARDIANS
AND CLEANERS OF THE OCEAN**

Empower the fisheries sector, namely professional fishers, to adopt more environmental-friendly fishing methods, prevent marine litter and increase responsible user behavior.

Create adequate conditions for the reception and treatment of litter at fishing ports, including through recycling and reuse.

Recognize and reward the volunteer service provided by fishers when retrieving marine litter that is passively collected in fishing gear.

AVOID

FISHING GEAR LOCATION WITH ACOUSTIC TAGS

Develop and engineer acoustic tags to be attached to fishing gear as a sustainable, low-cost and innovative low-impact solution to improve mapping, tracking and recovery of lost fishing gear.

Improve a robotic surface system linked with the acoustic tag system for lost fishing gear location/recovery.

MITIGATE

**DETECTION AND REMOVAL OF ABANDONED, LOST OR
OTHERWISE DISCARDED FISHING GEAR (ALDFG)**

Develop a system to detect ALDFG in the Ocean water column and seabed.

Co-develop, with fishers, a robotic tool to detect, map, track and recover ALDFG.

The three **NETTAG+** solutions will be tested, validated and demonstrated in real conditions in Atlantic and Mediterranean countries: Portugal, Spain, Italy, Croatia, Malta and United Kingdom

NETTAG+ main actions:

- ➔ **AWARENESS ACTIONS, PARTICIPATORY WORKSHOPS AND DEMONSTRATION EVENTS** with fishers on marine litter prevention and retrieval
- ➔ **ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACT ASSESSMENT OF ALDFG** and developed technological solutions
- ➔ **DEVELOPMENT AND TESTING OF SMART AND ENVIRONMENTAL-FRIENDLY SOLUTIONS FOR ALDFG** prevention and retrieval, through tagging, mapping and recovering technological systems
- ➔ **DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION ACTIONS** on NETTAG+ findings to policy-makers, industry, fishers, scientists, EU projects and the general public

What we aim to achieve:

- ➔ Successfully test and employ NETTAG+ tags to fishing gear to avoid lost and abandoned fishing gear (ALDFG)
- ➔ Work with fishers to be guardians and cleaners of our sea and tackling marine pollution.
- ➔ Contribute to Ocean health through retrieving operations and increased awareness.
- ➔ Reduce the negative impacts of ALDFG on marine life and habitats.

NETTAG+ brings together an international and multidisciplinary team from **7 different countries**, including scientists, the fishing industry, governmental fisheries authorities, NGOs, and technological and knowledge-management companies.

NETTAG+ targets groups:

Fishers

Fishing gear
manufacturers

Port
authorities

Policy
makers

Citizens

GOVERNMENT
OF MALTA

MINISTRY FOR AGRICULTURE,
FISHERIES AND ANIMAL RIGHTS
PARLIAMENTARY SECRETARIAT
FOR FISHERIES, AQUACULTURE
AND ANIMAL RIGHTS

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